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CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF MARKETIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION ON UNIVERSITY WEBSITES IN PAKISTAN

Corresponding & Author 1: **NAUMAN NASIM**, MPhil Scholar, Department of English, Air University Islamabad, Pakistan. Email: naumannasim23@gmail.com

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Abstract

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This study explores the marketization of higher education on university websites in Pakistan by drawing on critical discourse analysis. The process through which educational institutions have adopted market-oriented techniques as part of the competition in a neoliberal order is called 'marketization'. This research aims to investigate the linguistic features and discursive strategies employed on Pakistani university websites to depict the marketization of higher education. Using a qualitative research design within the tradition of Critical Discourse Analysis, the textual content of university websites was examined in this research. The research discovers several prominent linguistic features such as testimonials, positive framing, persuasive language, and an emphasis on employability and professional success. It also provides insights into the possible ramifications of marketization of the sector on the autonomy and values of universities, as well as on the process through which students make choices about their education and their experiences of it. The implications of our findings stress the importance of engaging critically with the processes of marketization taking place in higher education and urging universities and higher education systems to find a point of equilibrium between their market-oriented strategies on one hand and their fundamental educational purpose, on the other.

Keywords: Marketization, Testimonials, Persuasive, Discourse, Linguistic.

Introduction

Higher education marketization is the process by which higher educational institutions embrace a market-oriented mindset and practices whereby education is seen as a commodity, and students are customers. It employs market-style tactics within the higher education sector including price, competition, branding, and market positioning. Marketization brings elements of the free market to the area of education and with it the forces and dynamism that shape how universities operate and how education is imparted. It places a strong emphasis on the financial benefits and results of education, paying particular attention to things like employability, job possibilities, and return on investment. In line with the marketization paradigm, universities promote their distinct competitive advantages such as program rankings, accreditation, on-site amenities, and other selling points to attract students. They use marketing strategies to build and strengthen their brand image, enticing potential students with persuasive language, eye-catching design, and competitively-differentiating content. Text and images are used by colleges and universities to present and separate themselves from other institutions, promote their activities, and draw the attention of specific audiences such as potential students, benefactors, and alumni (Urciuoli, 2003). Language, whether textual or visual, is constantly and deliberately at work. The Internet is a primary avenue for communicating different institutional features through the official websites of higher education institutions. On university websites, discourse, or the mix of modalities of language in use (i.e., text, picture), generates strong messages. For many years, higher education remained completely immune to commercial forces. Terms from the commercial sector like "markets," "company identity," "mission statements," and "customers" have begun to appear in discourse practices in higher

education. Promotional elements are prevalent and regularly employed in several discourse genres used in higher education, including brochures, prospectuses, flyers, posters, employment advertisements, and home pages on websites (Fairclough, 1993). These sorts of discourse in higher education now focus more on marketing the university's qualities and convincing potential students to join, rather than just defining prerequisites and commitments and providing program information. Because of the loss in state financing and the pressure on a national and international level, universities have had to make use of a variety of sources to be financially in a better position (Askehave, 2007). Over the last two decades, there has been an increasing interest in researching the uses of language in professional and public contexts in general, and the effects of marketization on the discourses of higher education (Bhatia, 2004; Swales, 2004; Askehave, 2007; Osman, 2008). However, despite the growing influence of marketization in higher education at the policy level as well as in practice (Zollo, 2016; Osman, 2008; Askehave, 2007; Amjad & Shakir, 2014). A significant study by Fairclough (2013) utilizing critical discourse analysis on British university prospectuses demonstrates the shift toward the production of materials with promotional goals. Using critical discourse analysis, a scholar has compared how two Singaporean university prospectuses produce interpersonal meanings using visual and linguistic approaches (Teo, 2007). He saw that the standard practices of public universities' discourse preserved a relatively traditional self-centered authoritative voice by adopting a distant and impersonal tone. Pakistan has not been exempted from the worldwide phenomenon of market forces taking hold in the higher education sector. Pakistan's universities have felt more pressure in recent years to align themselves with neoliberal practices and philosophies to comply with market-driven

demands. The notion of "marketization" in higher education is not a phenomenon restricted to Pakistan. It is a worldwide accepted trend. Market-driven policies, according to authors such as [Marginson & Rhoades \(2002\)](#), are "redefining how universities operate." The marketization of higher education in Pakistan has had a unique trajectory, shaped by the country's somewhat distinct sociopolitical and economic issues. Pakistan's Higher Education Commission (HEC) has implemented several policies of putting market-driven strategies and performance-based funding in place. There have been studies on how marketization has reshaped higher education in Pakistan, but there remains a significant research gap in the analysis of universities' discursive approaches to responding to this phenomenon. This research, in the context of Pakistani higher education, looks at the language on their websites as a window into the underlying sociopolitical power structures, hierarchies, and socio-cultural implications of marketization. Through this critical scrutiny, this research sheds light on how this phenomenon is portrayed by Pakistani universities and the possible implications for the equality, quality, and accessibility of higher education. This study intends to contribute to academic discourse by initiating an inquiry into how market-oriented discourses are constructed and propagated through discourse digital platforms. The three-dimensional framework of Fairclough is employed in the study to see how the market-oriented discourses are being constructed in higher education and how form ensures the overt language details the informal power relations and the social structures.

Innovation / Research Gap

This research analyzes the discursive strategies of the universities to understand how marketization impacted the institutional identity, educational ideals, and the academia of Pakistan. Previous research has revealed not only the various linguistic strategies used by

universities around the world to navigate the competitive environment and attract potential students, but also the intricate ways in which language, power, and ideology intersect within the discourse of higher education marketization. However, a discernible gap remains when it comes to research into Pakistani university websites specifically. Therefore, this study seeks to address this gap by engaging in a systematic and thorough critical discourse analysis of university websites, and as such contribute to the larger scholarly conversation on higher education marketization and CDA.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it illustrates how institutions promote themselves through their websites. These market-based aspects are seen in the advertisement as a result of shifting socio-economic conditions throughout the world, which have altered social life as well as educational institution discourse orders. This subject is especially significant since discourse practices in higher education have evolved. There is now a need to generate bright, skilled, competent, and self-aware students to fulfill market demands for engaging students in a technology-based environment. This perception puts institutions under pressure to modify discursive practices such as the interaction between the institute and the students, the relationship between students and professors, teaching strategies, and teaching materials.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the reasons behind the use of appealing statements by educational institutes on their websites.
2. To analyze the various linguistic features employed by educational institutes.
3. To investigate how the text on university websites influences social interactions between the university and prospective students.

Research Questions

1. Why do institutes use appealing statements on websites?
2. How do educational institutes use different linguistic features for publicity on websites?
3. How does the text influence the social interactions between the university and the students?

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research methodology to demonstrate Fairclough's (1993) three-dimensional framework as an analytic tool to study the promotional discourses of universities. The framework allows for a systematic study of linguistic features in discursive practices that represent an important issue such as the promotion and publicity of academic institutions. The study employs this theoretical framework to show the intricate ways universities represent, project, and construct marketization discourses on their websites. Thus, Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is being employed here to unearth and understand the underlying power relations, ideologies, and discursive practices that construct this representation and how this representation of education is shaped within this market-oriented framework. CDA emerges as a fitting approach for delving into the marketization of higher education due to its capacity to unravel the multifaceted layers of power dynamics inherent in discursive constructions. Two public sector universities of Islamabad, Air University (AU), and Bahria University (BU) were selected for critical discourse analysis. The focus remained on promotional language and market-oriented components of higher education and discursive techniques remain categories for analysis. This deconstruction allows us to begin to reveal the linguistic features, discursive techniques, and rhetoric employed by universities to promote the market-oriented components of higher education. However, the research does not limit itself to linguistic components only; it

transcends them into a broader examination of discursive strategies such as employability, return on investment, and commercialization of education which universities also deploy to justify, legitimate, and argue their involvement in the marketization of higher education. This study traces how universities justify and legitimize their process of incorporation into the marketization of higher education.

Data Analysis

In this stage, Fairclough's 3D model is used to critically analyze selected university websites' text. The three levels of interpretation are text, interaction, and context. The data is taken from the websites of Air University Islamabad and Bahria University. For two reasons, the data is exclusively obtained from university websites. First, they are far more widely available than printed prospectuses. Second, because of its wide coverage and ease of use, the web has become a significant promotional tool for educational institutions. First is the website of Air University Islamabad.

Table 1: The Organizational Structure of Air University Website.

<i>University</i>	<i>About Us</i>
Air University	Vision and Mission
	Board of Governors
	Vice Chancellors Message
	Timeline
	Visit Air University
	AU Map
	Contact Us

These sections address the communicative intentions of various rhetorical strategies, discursive techniques, textual evidence of the influence of marketization, and the relationship between the institution and the students.

Vision:

"Air University aspires to be among the leading national universities, excelling in teaching, learning, research, innovation and public service." In this vision statement, Air University expresses its aspirations to be

counted among the leading national universities, and the statement makes it clear that the institution aspires to give the best teaching, learning, research, and innovation, engaged at the service of the public. The choice of wording shows a sense of ambition that encompasses a holistic devotion to striving to achieve academic excellence on various fronts as demanded by its vision.

Moves identified:

- a. Self-positioning: Seeing self as an aspirant to be among the leading national universities.
- b. Excellence: Aspire to excel in teaching, learning, research, innovation, and public service.

Mission:

The mission statement of Air University defines the intention of the university and focuses on chasing quality in the fields of learning and research. However, the statement stands out most about how it goes a step ahead to strive to ensure that the graduates are professionals imbued with qualities integral to their efforts. Additionally, the statement underscores the creation of a conducive environment that will motivate and inspire high-quality and innovative students, faculty, and other supporting services.

Moves identified:

- a. Excellence: striving to be par excellence at both teaching and researching.
- b. Graduate attributes: To be known for our graduates for their professionalism and integrity, social responsibility, and lifelong learning.
- c. Commitment to Environment: Ensuring an environment that will be chosen by the best students, faculty, and supporting staff.
- d. Contribution to society: Making a national contribution to a prosperous, peaceful, and enlightened society is a key aim.

The analysis indicates how languages play a role in marketing Air University as an institution devoted to quality and high standards, corporate social responsibility, and an agent of change in society. The positive use of the

languages and specific attributes integration is in line with higher education marketing discourses, targeting both potential students and other stakeholders. Using Fairclough's model here, it becomes obvious that the Activation and Macro Roles for the language present in both vision and mission have discursive implications beyond messaging those goals. Despite the lack of testimonies specifically mentioned in the remarks, the university's reputation is boosted using optimistic language and lofty goals, which act as an endorsement or positive portrayal. Institutions that follow market-oriented practices aim to entice the best and brightest. The mission's dedication to helping build a more affluent, peaceful, and enlightened society demonstrates a wider social effect, linking the university's objectives to the welfare of society. Both a representation of academic goals and a positioning tactic in the competitive academic landscape, the emphasis on "excellence" in teaching, learning, and research is important. The frequent use of phrases like "innovation" and "public service" helps to present the university in a positive light, making it seem progressive and socially active, meeting the modern demand for an all-encompassing institution.

Board of Governors

First and foremost, the website for Air University contains a "Board of Governors" section that names the key individuals responsible for managing and overseeing the institution's functioning. The board incorporates people with vast expertise in civilian life and military practice. The board includes many professions, from training to engineering to economics. The board's diverse composition may mirror the university's holistic educational background; however, it does show that it is attempting to gather individuals with different outlooks. The presentation language serves as a form of authority and a way to establish the board members' power and credibility. The accurate

description of the members' positions and professional distancing utilizing language promotes openness and professionalism. In addition, it is organized and structured consistent with the organizational patterns found in government papers. The language employed to describe the board members intentionally stresses their background, experience, and affiliations, all of which are discursive strategies. Finally, the "Board of Governors" section also illustrates the institution's aspiration to high achievement in collaborative governance and fit with the national interests and governance. A narrative surrounding the language components and discursive strategies illuminates the high aspiration of the university to portray itself as a responsible participant in Pakistan's competitive higher education market.

Vice Chancellor's Message

The welcoming remark from AU's Vice Chancellor is also placed in the "About Us" section, indicating its significance. A welcoming statement is gaining popularity and has recently been featured on an increasing number of university website homepages in Pakistan. The goal of this move is to express to readers the institution's pleasant and inviting attitude, assisting in the establishment of the first point of contact between the university and potential students.

Third-person subject

Air University, is a vibrant hub of academic distinction.

a) Ideological education

I endeavor to foster creativity and expression to enable our graduates to contribute at the national and global levels.

My keen focus would remain on synergizing multidisciplinary research to accrue benefits of upcoming creative technologies.

You will find the Air University campus brimming with life, offering modern facilities and opportunities to engage academically, socially, and culturally.

b) First-person/second-person pronoun

There is a conversational discourse in the vice chancellor's speech, which is typically from the authoritative one. According to Fairclough (1993), Confessionalization is one of the most obvious discursive shifts brought on by the commodification of social processes. Confessionalization, which is defined as "the simulation of private, face-to-face, person-to-person discourse in public mass-audience discourse" (print, radio, television), denotes on the one hand that there is growing equality between professionals and citizens as the latter have evolved from passive information receivers to active communication participants. A variety of rhetorical techniques, such as the use of first- and second-person pronouns, as well as sentiments of thankfulness and solidarity, serve as examples of this type of discourse. Some instances showing it in the text are given below.

I will endeavor to foster creativity and expression to enable our graduates.

My keen focus would remain on synergizing multidisciplinary research to accrue benefits of upcoming creative technologies.

You will find the Air University campus brimming with life.

I welcome you to a challenging, inspiring, and rewarding experience.

First-person pronouns make the text seem as though it is directly addressing the reader or the students who visit the website, the text feels more personal and increases the likelihood that the reader will be convinced and satisfied with that service.

c) Expressions of solidarity

These statements demonstrate the vice-chancellor and the university's desire to forge widespread unanimity among all parties involved. Such sentiments have the power to connect readers to the university and foster a sense of belonging. Additionally, the phrase "our graduates" strengthens the emotional ties between the university and the graduates,

adding to the impression of the two parties' close ties.

"I will endeavor to foster creativity and expression to enable our graduates to contribute at the national and global levels".

"You will find the Air University campus brimming with life, offering modern facilities and opportunities to engage academically, socially, and culturally".

In the first text above the writer uses our graduates to create a bond between the university and the visitors, those visiting the website may be for admission. In the second instance above he has given the outcomes that a student can experience and will experience if join their university.

d) Expressions of gratitude

To strengthen the position of the readers and reduce the "imbalance "between the university and the readers, the vice chancellor employs "politeness methods." The VC has now largely abandoned his supremacy and shown the greatest amount of respect to the readers, best illuminating the conversational zed aspect of the greeting comment.

"On behalf of the Air University team, I welcome you".

Time Line

Air University's timeline highlights the institution's historical progress and milestones through several moves and events. Using CDA on the timeline, we can see how various discursive strategies and linguistic traits relate to the study's goal of deciphering the language's representation of the marketization of higher education. The appointment of important individuals, such as the Vice-Chancellor, in January 2001 indicates the beginning of the timeline and indicates a strategic shift in the university's leadership. August and November 2001 documents titled "Feasibility Report" and "Inspection" reveal a bureaucratic tone, drawing attention to the formalities of the university's establishment. More importantly, some moves have been made in response to the grand narrative about

organizational development and strategic planning.

AU Map

Air University's "AU Map" section makes use of CDA to understand the discursive strategies and linguistic elements used. The primary objective of this part is to direct potential students to the university's main campus, which can be found at PAF Complex, E-9 Islamabad. The goal of providing phone numbers and fax information is to make it easier to communicate and get in touch. When viewed through the prism of Fairclough's model, this section largely serves to inform and facilitate. The language used to provide contact information is practical and serves the objective of making it easier for people to contact the university. Furthermore, there is a disclaimer within the section that indicates the length of time the information presented in the prospectus is relevant. It states that this information was accurate as of printing, the prospectus is intended to act as a general guide and not as a legally binding contract. Since the educational state changes and policies, programs, and prices could vary, this brief part aligns with Fairclough's notion of intertextuality. Proactively removing any potential disparities due to adjustments ensures that the university is protected.

Contact Us

In the "Contact Us" section various contact details for key personnel within the university are provided. Everyone from students and parents to anybody else looking for information or help from the university can find what they need in this section, which is designed to make contact easier. In line with the overarching goal of improving stakeholder participation, the next step is to set up an easily understood and accessible channel of communication A commitment to candor and openness is also implied in the text by names, titles, office addresses, phone numbers, and email addresses of persons like the Registrar, Vice Chancellor, Directors, and other

department heads being shared. By enabling the ability to properly represent the institution's structure and important contacts, this change is compliant with Fairclough's model. Moreover, the text arrangement of specific contacts for different affiliations, starting with the Vice Chancellor Secretariat, Administration & Support, Academics, International Cooperation Office, etc., seems to be using language strategically to provide a picture of the university, where everybody is readily available and willing to reply. It makes sense in the context of the marketization of higher education: in the modern world, institutions strive to make themselves appear client-oriented and service-focused. These traits confirm Air University's adherence to Fairclough's model by adjusting to the current reality of a highly competitive market where only the most adaptable can survive.

Table 2: The Organizational Structure of Bahria University Website.

<i>University</i>	<i>About the US</i>
Bahria University	Rector's Message
	Why Bahria
	Vision and Mission
	BU At a Glance
	Jobs
	Board of Governors
	Office Directory
	Contact us

Rector's Message

The language employed by the Rector reflects Bahria University's position as a premier public sector institution committed to addressing contemporary challenges. Therefore, the language emphasizes the Rector's oath to the future leaders and innovators that says he shall empower them through faculty, resources, environment, and technology. The vision aligns with the marketization language through the strategic philosophical statement that Bahria will combine theory and practice and ensure cultured and personalized research. Therefore,

the Bahria University discourse makes the university more attractive to the market by representing it as an already engaged knowledge generator, and diffuser for market needs. The more, the speech articulates the character, decency, honesty, and consideration attributes that reflect the traditional educational basics and in parallel emphasizes the need to develop oneself without just research and academic activities.

Why Bahria

This section commences with the tagline "Why Bahria?" to conceptually frame the content as the reasons why a reader should choose Bahria University over any other alternatives. This represents a rhetorical strategy to appeal to the audience's rationality and choice-making mechanisms, positioning Bahria University as a viable option. This section should then have complied with a list of characteristics that showcase all of the above-mentioned features and offerings of Bahria University. Such characteristics function as rhetorical skills that are carefully crafted to argue for the university's merits and competitive edge. For example, it is claimed that the university is government-chartered, HEC recognized, and its programs are accredited by PEC, PMDC, and PBC. Such attributes aim to raise the university's credibility and position in the education space. In addition, the mention of a competent faculty, purpose-built campuses, modern labs, and well-equipped libraries demonstrates the University's commitment to academic excellence and infrastructure development. These linguistic strategies aim to create a notion of credibility and professionalism, aligning them with customer-oriented marketplace expectations of higher education institutions. Finally, the statement of merit/need-based scholarships, disabled seats, and under-developed region quotas also implies the University's commitment to variety and social responsibility.

BU At a Glance

The language represents an institution that not only exists but is also trustworthy and authoritative in the higher learning sector. This aligns with Fairclough's definition of intertextuality because the institution is framed within the broader academic discourses of certification and recognition to enhance credibility and attract potential stakeholders. The section also presents an image of the University committed to high levels of instruction, acquisition, and knowledge. This can align with market-oriented discourses, which function under the notion that students must be guaranteed their money or effort's worth, hence globally competitive. The high level of language such as "highest standards," "compatible with global requirements," and "preparing professionals," shows that Bahria University presents itself as a center of academic excellence and professional growth. All this is aimed at acquiring visibility and attractiveness, showing that the institution is big and provides opportunities across the country.

Jobs

The language in this section is aimed at attracting potential job applicants for different positions at the university. One of the language changes relates to the use of imperative sentences where they read, "Download the application form," making it imperative for the reader to take action. The change in the language is, therefore, aimed at presenting the university as an actor who guides students on what to do and warns them about the pressing needs, thus causing a sense of urgency. Additionally, the section contains the last update date, which helps humanity determine the timeline within which the information was posted and whether it is still relevant. The action correlates with Fairclough's idea of intertextuality, where texts tend to refer to other texts or backgrounds in establishing authenticity and authority. Therefore, by listing the most recent change, the university proves

its integrity and timely communication with prospective job applicants. As a result, the university presents itself as modern and responsive to candidates' diverse needs. Additionally, the listing of specific job positions and their related dates indicate the university's initiative in finding quality personnel. Each position is accompanied by a proper job description that outlines the necessary qualifications and functions. Lastly, the section ends with the contact details of the Director of Human Resources, helping the applicants to know where to ask for help or seek clarification.

Board of Governors

This section provides an overview of power relations and institutional affiliations that may impact the decision-making processes of Bahria University. Hence, about the governors, the analysis reveals a strong presence of military leaders. In this way, the influence of the military on university governance is evident, which is related to the fact that Bahria University is related to the state's armed forces. Similarly, the Rector is a designated high naval official, which also demonstrates Bahria University's strong connection with the military. This integration is the result of a predefined strategy to capitalize on military prestige and opportunities to create a safe and secure academic market environment.

Office Directory

The section presents useful information to its stakeholders who may need information about whom to contact on various administrative and academic matters within the university. The linguistic structures used in the section provide both the form and function of language. For example, the syntactic structure's use of the terms "DG Islamabad Campus," "Director Admin," and "HOD" can be understood as a pyramid structure popular in academic organizations. The linguistic text-forming in the section builds the authority and power of the institution, which in turn reflects the dynamics of power in the university setting.

Besides, the language used to list people by name, role, and contact information relies on the functional use of language. But from a discursive point of view, it also contributes to the institutional visibility and validity of their roles. The ability of teachers, students, and staff to access such information is part of a current convention in higher education in which there is an attempt to establish a culture of contact between all involved. Moreover, the position and authority are discursively supported using official names and terms.

Contact Us

The section starts with a summary of the most recent update, ensuring readers receive up-to-date information. The information includes addresses, phone numbers, fax numbers, and Google Maps links to Bahria University's many campuses and affiliated schools. From a linguistic standpoint, the section employs straightforward and informative language to make it easier to locate contact information for various university organizations. The use of uniform addresses and phone numbers increases clarity and accessibility. However, some advances in this section reflect more general discursive tactics inherent in higher education marketization. Another significant move is the deliberate inclusion of Google Maps links next to each address. This move highlights the physical presence and accessibility of Bahria University's campuses and all its related institutions. In this regard, it best fits marketization discourses, which advocate for the enhanced importance of physical infrastructure and geographical behavior to access students and other stakeholders. Additionally, the utilization of a UAN number for the Islamabad campus demonstrates the institution's commitment to improved accessibility to information and services for a broader audience.

Findings

The analysis of both the website structure and sections provided great insights into the

institution's communicative goals, rhetorical strategies, discursive approaches, and certain language parts. One of the most general and independent findings is the rational, purposive, and goal-oriented coherence between language and discourse, which matches the market-oriented goals. Thus, Air University markets itself to prospective students as a perfect place positively praising itself, setting high aspirations to achieve, stressing the importance of excellence, integrity, and social responsibility among graduates and other stakeholders. Such perception is justified by English-language terms such as university "aspires to be among the leading national universities" and "aiming for excellence in teaching and research", which place the institution in a specific university market type that promises a top-quality service. Self-positioning; exalting excellence; promoting graduate qualities; optimizing the environment; and showing reformative and transformational impact on society are the more overall, top-down strategies utilized in most divisions. However, they are not designed only to attract prospective students but to construct the institution's myth to match the market's interests. For instance, the detailed information of the Board of Governors, drawn from diverse backgrounds, affiliations, different experiences, and different personalities helps to achieve its credibility, legitimacy, and other informants. Air University is in a discursive contest of nonstop progress, adaptability, and global equivalence. These exemplary sections feature informative, descriptive, and pragmatic language signs that showcase the institution's willingness to provide a good experience. Likewise, Bahria University's website structure and content would exhibit which strategies the University uses to attract and persuade students and the general marketing of higher education through websites analyzed using Fairclough's CDA model. It underscores in the Rector's Message the university's initiatives to train future

leaders, promote innovation, and inspire social reform. Language marketing contemporary education policies like those that focus on knowledge-led development and learning-market language such as associates soft global competition and gravity are used in the language. Bahria University uses descriptive language to define the character of each campus site and its many features, each of which can appeal to a broad range of students' preferences and interests. Bahria University has grown more transparent, open, and vigorous by offering touch information for the numerous administrators and academics working in the university. It will enhance stakeholder beliefs in the justice and trustworthiness of the university. It was also revealed that universities use promising statements on their websites to create a positive image and appeal to potential students. By promoting a positive organizational image, such statements contribute to the credibility of the institute and its reputation in the eyes of stakeholders. Websites that make promising statements can be emotionally engaging for visitors and they can instill a sense of belonging and the feeling of being marginal to the group. In the marketplace of higher education, institutes strive to distinguish themselves from peers, as it is an extremely competitive environment. Institutes highlight their specifics, unique projects, or accomplished achievements to target certain target audiences. Education institutions purposely use precultural means such as persuasive language and writing style. Certain language tactics can promote a sense of belonging and help establish a favorable first impression, such as intersectional language or storytelling providing students with a personal perspective on study. Special phonetic and lexical means are possibly used for separate target audiences according to consumer characteristics. Depending on cultural, social, and personal characteristics, certain linguistic facilities can be bridgeable and effective in

attracting and persuading the website user. For institutes, it is important to provide short and simple textual content on the website. They strive to provide the website with simple information comprising understandable features for quick perception by the user. Students and the institution's communications' overall tone and nature are affected by the language employed in online communication. On the other hand, textual cues influence students' oration to establish a social group with the institution, such as formality, approachability, or friendliness. For instance, empathetic communication and the use of clear, simple language improve the quality of verbal or text message exchanges between universities and students. Respectful, inclusive, and friendly language creates a comfortable, and welcoming atmosphere. Additionally, having access to essential tools like FAQs, message boards, and contact information makes forming a social group with the institution a breeze.

Conclusion

In such a globally integrated world, the marketization movement has led to radical innovations in a variety of spheres, including the higher educational market of Pakistan. The best students are now being chosen by universities from the pool of candidates, and the best universities are chosen by students, who have more options to choose from in the contemporary higher educational market. Corporal advertising mechanism introduced into universities was primarily used to draw the attention of students and to violently persuade them against their choice of attending a different institution. At the discourse level, such marketization is characterized by a range of higher education genres.

Recommendations

Future scholars could do a comparative investigation of marketization strategies on university websites in various regions of Pakistan to find regional differences and underlying sociocultural effects. Researchers

could also conduct surveys or interviews to explore the impact of such marketized language on student perceptions and decisions.

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